
Communication Before Computation: The Development of Communicative Structure in Transformer Learning

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Abstract

Transformer language models coordinate computation across independently parameterized layers through a shared residual stream, yet the developmental process of this coordination remains poorly understood. We track the formation of inter-layer communicative structure across training in six models spanning four model families (Pythia, BLOOM, OLMo-2, TinyLlama). In the two families with dense early checkpoints (Pythia and OLMo-2), we observe a stereotyped developmental sequence: adjacent layers first align their dominant MLP transformation directions, establishing a shared communicative backbone; spectral restructuring then concentrates energy along these aligned directions, propagating as a backward cascade from the output layers. The mature form of the resulting communicative protocol depends on the activation function. GELU models (Pythia, BLOOM) consolidate weight-level alignment into a persistent, fixed-geometry communication channel. SwiGLU models (OLMo-2, TinyLlama) undergo sustained decoherence of static alignment, with coordination transferring to the learned gate, which dynamically selects shared effective subspaces as a function of the input. Preliminary analysis of the attention OV circuit reveals a similar pattern: weight-level alignment surges during backbone formation and then collapses, consistent with the attention pattern assuming the coordination role. This parallels the distinction between fixed and context-dependent communication subspaces documented across cortical circuits, suggesting that the static/dynamic dichotomy may be a general feature of coordination through shared subspaces in modular systems.

1 Introduction

Transformer language models coordinate computation across independently parameterized layers through a shared residual stream, which serves as the sole medium of inter-layer communication [Elhage et al., 2021, Vaswani et al., 2017]. Recent work has revealed considerable structure in how this communication is organized in trained models. Layers read from and write to low-rank subspaces of the residual stream, forming communication channels whose singular vectors are semantically interpretable [Millidge and Black, 2022, Merullo et al., 2024]. The Jacobians of successive transformer blocks align their top singular vectors with one another, a phenomenon first identified in ResNets [Li and Pappayan, 2023] and subsequently confirmed in transformers, where it correlates with model performance [Aubry et al., 2024]. These structural subspaces have been shown to mediate specific computational motifs, including inhibition, duplicate detection, and induction [Merullo et al., 2024, Olsson et al., 2022]. A parallel line of work on training dynamics has documented that transformers undergo sharp phase transitions early in training, during which capabilities like in-context learning emerge abruptly alongside the formation of identifiable circuits [Olsson et al., 2022, Singh et al., 2024], and that early training is marked by representation collapse

and spectral reorganization [Gallego-Feliciano et al., 2025, Aubry et al., 2024]. What this body of work has not provided is a developmental account describing how communicative structure is assembled across training. We trace this process directly, tracking how inter-layer communicative structure forms across training in six models spanning four model families.

We find that transformer models solve the inter-layer communication problem through a stereotyped developmental sequence. In the earliest phase of training, adjacent layers align their dominant MLP transformation directions, establishing a shared set of residual stream subspaces through which information can accumulate coherently across depth. This communicative backbone forms rapidly and is followed by spectral restructuring that concentrates energy along directions shared across layers. This restructuring proceeds as a cascade originating at the output end of the network, propagating backward toward the input layers.

This problem of cross-module communication is not unique to transformers. In neuroscience, the same problem arises at the level of cortical areas, which must selectively route information to one another despite lacking centralized control over their interactions. Semedo et al. [2019] demonstrated that communication between visual cortical areas V1 and V2 occurs through a low-dimensional communication subspace. Subsequent work has shown that such communication subspaces appear across the cortical hierarchy [Perich et al., 2018, Gallego et al., 2020, Srinath et al., 2021, Young et al., 2025] and that a source population can maintain multiple, overlapping subspaces in which routing choices are activity-dependent [MacDowell et al., 2025]. The relevant finding from this literature is that the brain employs at least two distinct strategies for inter-area coordination: relatively fixed communication channels, particularly in early sensory areas, and dynamic, context-dependent routing through input-gated subspace selection in associative regions [Fries, 2015, Kohn et al., 2020].

We find that transformer language models implement both strategies, with the architectural choice of activation function determining which one dominates. Models using GELU activations (the Pythia family and BLOOM) build a static protocol that, once established, generally persists for the remainder of training. Models using SwiGLU activations (OLMo-2 and TinyLlama) initially follow the same trajectory but then undergo a sustained decoherence of weight-level alignment, with the coordination role transferring from static weight subspaces to an input-dependent gate. This architectural bifurcation parallels the distinction between fixed and dynamic communication strategies documented in cortical circuits. While we do not claim a shared mechanism, the convergence on the same two-strategy taxonomy across biological and artificial systems suggests that the distinction between static and input-gated communication may reflect a general constraint on how modular systems learn to exchange information. Moreover, the communicative shift seen in SwiGLU models suggests that input-gated communication is more expressive, yet more difficult to establish, than its static alternative.

Together, these findings offer a longitudinal account of how transformer layers learn to communicate, connecting the well-characterized communicative structure of trained models to the training dynamics that produce it.

2 Pythia models and measurements

To trace the developmental sequence outlined above, we use models with controlled variation and dense checkpoint coverage.

We use Pythia models of the following sizes: 410M, 1B, and 1.4B parameters. These models share a common training corpus (the Pile) and tokenizer, differing only in width (d_{model}) and depth (n_{layers}). The 410M and 1.4B share the same depth (24 layers) but differ in width (1024 vs. 2048), while the 1B and 1.4B share the same width (2048) but differ in depth (16 vs. 24 layers). We analyze checkpoints at steps 0 (initialization), 128, 512, 2,000, 8,000, 32,000, 64,000, and 143,000.

We track three families of measurements across training. First, the principal subspace overlap between layers’ composed MLP products. Each transformer layer’s MLP performs an up-projection followed by a down-projection; the composed product $W_{\text{down}}W_{\text{up}}$ is a square matrix in the residual stream’s ambient space whose singular vectors identify the directions along which the MLP reads from and writes to the residual stream. For each pair of layers, we compute the cosines of the principal angles between their top- k singular vector subspaces, and compare these to the expected overlap of random

subspaces of the same dimensionality in the same ambient space. This is our most direct probe of inter-layer communicative alignment.

Second, the singular value spectrum of the composed product at each layer. From this, we derive the effective rank (the exponential of the entropy of the normalized squared singular values). At initialization, the composed product follows the Marchenko–Pastur distribution expected of a product of random matrices; departure from this distribution reflects structure imposed by training.

Third, the discrete cosine transform (DCT) of the hidden-state trajectory across layers, which we use to corroborate the subspace overlap results. For a model with L layers, we extract the hidden state at each layer for a fixed set of input tokens and compute the DCT across the layer dimension. We summarize this spectrum with its normalized spectral entropy.

We use these measures in Section 2.1 to confirm that the cross-layer alignment detected by subspace overlap has consequences for the residual stream’s dynamics.

2.1 Communication as the first priority

We begin with the measurement most directly relevant to communicative structure: the degree to which adjacent layers share a common set of directions for exchanging information. For each pair of adjacent layers, we compute the mean cosine similarity between the top- k singular vector subspaces of their respective composed MLP products ($W_{\text{down}}W_{\text{up}}$), and compare this to the expected overlap of random subspaces of the same dimensionality in the same ambient space.

Figure 1: Mean adjacent-layer top-10 subspace overlap across training for Pythia-410M, Pythia-1B, and Pythia-1.4B, compared to random baseline. Alignment grows slowly from steps 0 to 128, and then rapidly accelerates between steps 128 and 512.

At initialization, adjacent layers’ structural subspaces overlap no more than random chance would predict. Between steps 128 and 512, this overlap surges in all three models, meaning the dominant transformation directions at each layer are rapidly aligning with those of their neighbors (Figure 1). This alignment reshapes the trajectory of the residual stream (Figure 2).

(a) Normalized DCT energy spectrum of the hidden-state trajectory across layers for Pythia-1.4B at steps 0 and 512. The pattern in the right panel is consistent across all three model scales.

(b) Normalized spectral entropy of the hidden-state DCT spectrum across training for Pythia-410M, Pythia-1B, and Pythia-1.4B. Across models, spectral entropy reaches its minimum at step 512.

Figure 2: DCT analysis of hidden-state trajectories.

The residual architecture is, by design, one where the initial signal changes slowly across layers. In a randomly initialized transformer, many of these transformations will cancel out, and this combination means that an initialized transformer will have a very smooth trajectory. In the DCT decomposition (Figure 2a), this manifests as a significant amount of energy in the lowest frequencies ($k = 0$ and $k = 1$).

The alignment shown in Figure 1 creates a subset of directions that can accumulate across layers without canceling out, attenuating some of the random cancellation. This leads to even smoother trajectories, visible in the increase in low frequency energy from steps 0 to 512.

The normalized spectral entropy, which captures the uniformity of energy across frequencies, confirms this concentration (Figure 2b). The dip between steps 0 and 512 reflects the emergence of structure, as energy concentrates in an increasingly small number of components. Importantly, spectral entropy resurges after this point, indicating a phase shift that occurs after structure is built.

2.2 Building on structure

By step 512, the layers have created a communicative backbone, enabling computational coordination. They then build on this backbone for the rest of training, and we can track this process with additional measurements.

The composed effective rank at the first and last layers collapses immediately after the communicative subspace is formed (Figure 3). The reorganization is reflected in the singular value spectrum of the composed product, which changes substantially between steps 512 and 2,000 (Figure 4).

The cross-layer alignment that is established by step 512 creates a distinction between directions that matter and directions that do not. Along directions where layers are aligned, additions to the residual stream point the same way and accumulate. Along directions where they are unaligned, additions point in unrelated directions and partially cancel. Over the subsequent training steps, this bias reshapes the individual spectra: the aligned directions grow, the unaligned ones are suppressed, and the heavy tail separates from the bulk.

2.3 Emergence of depth specialization

The effective rank trajectories at early and late layers diverge after the initial collapse (Figures 3a, 3b). At layer 0, the composed effective rank drops, then eventually recovers to a higher rank than it started. At the final layer, the composed effective rank drops, and stays around this low point for the rest of training. The underlying cause becomes apparent in the evolution of the full singular value distribution across training (Figure 5).

Figure 3: Composed effective rank ($W_{down}W_{up}$) across training for Pythia-410M, Pythia-1B, and Pythia-1.4B at layer 0 (a) and the final layer (b). Both layers show a sharp drop after step 512, but diverge afterward: layer 0 rebounds and ultimately expands beyond its initialized value, while the final layer remains compressed.

Figure 4: Singular value spectrum of the composed MLP product ($W_{down}W_{up}$) at the final layer for Pythia-410M, Pythia-1B, and Pythia-1.4B at steps 0, 512, and 2,000. The spectrum is flat at initialization and remains so at step 512 despite the cross-layer alignment already established in Figure 1. By step 2,000, a heavy tail has separated from the bulk.

Following the emergence of communicative structure, the model begins implementing depth specialization. Between steps 512 and 2,000, bulk-tail distributions begin to differentiate depending on depth, and these differences are exacerbated throughout the rest of training.

At layer 0, the structural subspace consists of one direction with magnitude ~ 2.5 times that of the bulk. At the final layer, the top direction sits at roughly 6 times the bulk, the second at 4 times, the third and fourth at around 3 times, and so on through a gradual taper. No single direction dominates as sharply as layer 0’s spike, but the cumulative effect is far greater: a dozen directions each carrying several times the bulk’s energy collectively capture a much larger share of the total than one direction at 2.5 times ever could. This is why we see the higher rank at layer 0, as energy is less concentrated in the dominant directions.

Inter-layer communication emerges as a cascade originating where the training signal is strongest (Figure 6). Across all three models, the coupling between the final two layers peaks at step 512. Other layer boundaries show a similar increase, though the magnitude of this increase generally weakens with distance from the output. Most of these other layers then peak at step 2,000, in the same time frame that the final layers drop in coherence.

This pullback at the final layers coincides with the widening of the communication channel (Table 1). At step 512, the coupling between the final layers is concentrated in a small number of directions. Between steps 512 and 2,000, the spectral restructuring documented in Figure 4 creates additional structurally significant directions, and the coupling spreads across them.

Figure 5: Singular value spectrum of the composed MLP product ($W_{down}W_{up}$) for Pythia-1.4B at layers 0 (a), 12 (b), and 23 (c), at steps 512, 2,000, and 143,000. Layer 0 develops a single dominant direction above an elevated bulk, the middle layer shows intermediate concentration with a gradually tapering tail, and the final layer shows the smoothest transition from tail to bulk.

Model	Step 512		Step 2,000		Step 8,000	
	top-5	top-50	top-5	top-50	top-5	top-50
<i>Final layer boundary</i>						
Pythia-410M	0.602	0.391	0.360 (−40%)	0.493 (+26%)	0.624 (+73%)	0.352 (−29%)
Pythia-1B	0.579	0.375	0.258 (−55%)	0.484 (+29%)	0.667 (+158%)	0.371 (−23%)
Pythia-1.4B	0.848	0.473	0.421 (−50%)	0.549 (+16%)	0.560 (+33%)	0.446 (−19%)
<i>Middle layer boundary</i>						
Pythia-410M	0.285	0.309	0.307 (+8%)	0.553 (+79%)	0.205 (−33%)	0.456 (−18%)
Pythia-1B	0.398	0.296	0.398 (0%)	0.488 (+65%)	0.586 (+47%)	0.504 (+3%)
Pythia-1.4B	0.505	0.364	0.591 (+17%)	0.570 (+57%)	0.580 (−2%)	0.511 (−10%)

Table 1: Mean cosine similarity between top- k singular vector subspaces at the final and middle layer boundaries across three training stages. Percentage changes are relative to the preceding step. At the final boundary, the coupling follows a three-stage cycle: initially concentrated in a narrow beam (high top-5 at step 512), it redistributes into a broader subspace by step 2,000 (top-5 drops 40–55%, top-50 rises 16–29%), then reconsolidates by step 8,000 (top-5 recovers, top-50 retreats). At the middle boundary, all subspace widths increase uniformly between steps 512 and 2,000, reflecting simultaneous alignment and spectral restructuring, then plateau or begin their own redistribution.

At the final boundary, top-5 overlap drops sharply between steps 512 and 2,000, while top-50 overlap holds steady or increases (Table 1). The middle layers show no such divergence because they are experiencing the alignment wave and the spectral restructuring simultaneously. Then, between steps 2,000 and 8,000, top-5 overlap recovers, and top-50 overlap reverts back, likely constituting a spectral recalibration following the restructuring of the earlier layers.

Together, these measurements reveal a three-stage cycle at the final boundary (Table 1). At step 512, the final two layers are aligned along their most dominant directions, although at this point, the singular values of these directions are only marginally larger than those of the less dominant directions. Between steps 512 and 2,000, the dominant singular values begin to separate from the bulk, and this is happening across the entire model. As a result, energy is being rearranged across many directions simultaneously, which temporarily smears the coupling. Once the tail stabilizes, the updated set of dominant directions reassert themselves and the top- k coupling snaps back, but now those directions carry real spectral weight.

2.4 Competition among endpoints

The only other couplings that share the final layers’ peak and pullback pattern are those of the first two layer boundaries. These boundaries sit at the beginning of the forward pass, where the token embedding provides structured input statistics before the network itself becomes structured. The final layers sit at the beginning of the backward pass, where the gradient from the loss provides a similarly structured signal. Both ends of the network are anchored by a clean signal, which may be

Figure 6: Cross-layer coherence resolved by depth. (Top) Top-10 subspace overlap between adjacent layers across training for Pythia-410M, Pythia-1B, and Pythia-1.4B, shown per layer boundary. (Bottom) The same data as a heatmap, with layer boundary on the y-axis and training step on the x-axis.

why their layer boundaries are the first to align: one consistent input is sufficient to drive commitment, whereas the middle layers must wait for the structure to propagate inward before either their forward or backward signals carry enough coherence to align around.

Although both ends commit early, the final layer’s protocol is far stronger, and this strength determines the direction of propagation. In the steps following the initial commitment, the coupling at the first two layer boundaries drops back toward baseline and does not recover until late in training. Meanwhile, the coupling at the final layer boundaries recovers quickly, and the alignment wave propagates backward through the network. It seems that the gradient signal, which carries the structure of the final layers’ subspace, progressively overwrites whatever alignment the early layers initially found. The early intermediate layers, caught between the two anchors’ competing spheres of influence, reach peak coupling much later than the rest of the network (Figure 6). We can tentatively infer that the early layers’ initial protocol is built, wiped, then slowly replaced with that of the final layers.

The pairwise subspace overlap between all layer pairs provides a more complete view of this backward propagation (Figure 7). Across all three models, a block of mutual alignment forms among the final layers by step 512 and extends toward the input end over subsequent training. The specific pattern of propagation varies with model scale, but the direction is consistent.

3 Beyond Pythia

3.1 OLMo-2

The developmental sequence documented above was observed in Pythia models, which share a common architecture, training corpus, and tokenizer. To test whether these formation dynamics generalize beyond the Pythia family, we repeat the subspace overlap and SVD spectrum analyses

Figure 7: Pairwise top-10 subspace overlap between all layer pairs across training for Pythia-410M (top), Pythia-1B (middle), and Pythia-1.4B (bottom), at each checkpoint from initialization to step 143,000.

on OLMo-2-1B, a 16-layer, 2048-dimensional model from the OLMo-2 family [Groeneveld et al., 2024], which provides intermediate checkpoints at early and late stages. OLMo-2 differs from Pythia in several respects relevant to our analysis: it uses SwiGLU activations rather than GELU, applies attention and the MLP sequentially rather than in parallel, and is trained on a distinct data mixture. OLMo-2-1B was also trained for much longer, with checkpoints up to step 1,000,000, compared to Pythia’s 143,000.

OLMo-2-1B exhibits the same early surge in cross-layer alignment observed in the Pythia models (Figure 8; cf. Figure 1). Here, it occurs between steps 1,000 and 6,000, later and longer than the 128–2,000 range we saw in the Pythia models. This difference in length is likely, at least in part, due to differences in checkpoint density, as Pythia lacks a checkpoint between steps 2,000 and 8,000.

A bulk-tail separation in the singular value spectrum emerges during the same period of rapid alignment (Figure 9). Unlike the Pythia models, where alignment is largely complete by step 512 and spectral restructuring does not begin until afterward, the two processes overlap in OLMo’s available checkpoints. This co-occurrence raises two sources of ambiguity. The first is checkpoint sparsity: OLMo lacks checkpoints between steps 0 and 1,000, so the alignment surge could have begun earlier than our first measurement captures, compressing what is actually a sequential process into an apparently simultaneous one. The second concerns the relationship between the two processes within the overlapping window. The dynamics are not identical: cross-layer alignment rises steeply between steps 1,000 and 3,000 and then decelerates, while bulk-tail separation is modest at step 2,000 and accelerates through step 3,000 and beyond. This staggering is consistent with alignment establishing a directional bias that spectral restructuring then exploits, as argued for the Pythia models in Section 2.2, but the temporal overlap prevents the clean dissociation that would make this ordering unambiguous.

The depth-resolved overlap trajectories provide a finer-grained view of this cascade (Figure 10). As in the Pythia models (Figure 6), the initial surge begins at the final layers and cascades backward through the majority of the network.

Unlike the Pythia models, OLMo-2-1B does not show a sharp rise in cross-layer coherence in the first layers; the coherence between layer 0 and 1 does not rapidly accelerate at step 1,000, nor does it

Figure 8: Mean adjacent-layer top-10 subspace overlap across training for OLMo-2-1B, compared to random baseline. The same early surge in cross-layer alignment observed in the Pythia models (Figure 1) appears here despite differences in activation function, attention-MLP ordering, and training data.

Figure 9: Top-50 singular values of the composed MLP product ($W_{down}W_{up}$) at the final layer for OLMo-2-1B at steps 0, 1,000, 2,000, and 3,000. As in the Pythia models (Figure 4), the spectrum is mostly flat at initialization. By step 2,000, a heavy tail begins separating from the bulk, coinciding with the period of rapid cross-layer alignment documented in Figure 8.

peak any higher than later layers. This may be because the sequential architecture of OLMo prevents the first MLP from receiving a clean embedding signal, instead receiving a signal modified by the first attention block. This may also be caused by the SwiGLU activation function, which has a major impact on the overall coherence trajectory (Section 3.2).

Unlike the Pythia models, OLMo-2-1B does not exhibit a spike, pullback, and recovery pattern at the final layer boundary. Instead, the coupling rises for a few thousand steps, starts gradually declining

Figure 10: Cross-layer coherence resolved by depth for OLMo-2-1B.

around step 5,000, and never recovers. In the Pythia models, this coincided with the widening of the communication channel. OLMo exhibits the same channel widening: at the final boundary, top-5 overlap drops 8% between steps 2,000 and 5,000 while top-50 overlap rises 32%, but the magnitude of this redistribution is substantially attenuated relative to the Pythia models (Table 7), which explains the absence of the transient dip.

The pairwise overlap matrix across all layer pairs confirms that OLMo follows the same backward cascade documented in the Pythia models (Figure 11; cf. Figure 7): a block of mutual alignment forms among the final layers and gradually extends toward the input end.

Figure 11: Pairwise top-10 subspace overlap between all layer pairs across training for OLMo-2-1B, at each checkpoint from initialization to step 1,000,000. As in the Pythia models (Figure 7), a block of mutual alignment forms among the final layers and extends toward the input end over subsequent training. The cascade attenuates before reaching the earliest layers, consistent with the weak early-boundary coherence documented in Figure 10.

Boundary	OLMo-2-1B					Pythia-1B				
	10k	100k	500k	1M	Δ	8k	32k	64k	143k	Δ
0–1	0.107	0.134	0.219	0.218	+103%	0.137	0.197	0.178	0.174	+27%
4–5	0.510	0.174	0.147	0.146	−71%	0.562	0.473	0.427	0.397	−29%
7–8	0.586	0.455	0.307	0.259	−56%	0.497	0.591	0.558	0.490	−1%
10–11	0.607	0.552	0.376	0.314	−48%	0.516	0.598	0.578	0.475	−8%
14–15	0.531	0.338	0.228	0.214	−60%	0.529	0.611	0.612	0.562	+6%
Overall	0.472	0.369	0.290	0.256	−46%	0.482	0.494	0.466	0.417	−14%

Table 2: Top-10 subspace overlap at selected layer boundaries across late training for OLMo-2-1B and Pythia-1B. Both models begin this window with similar coherence profiles, but OLMo undergoes sustained decoherence at all boundaries except 0–1, while Pythia remains approximately stable. Percentage change (Δ) is computed between the first and last step shown for each model.

3.2 Decoherence and activation functions

The preceding analyses show that OLMo-2-1B and the Pythia models follow similar trajectories during the formation of communicative structure. Where the two diverge is in what happens after this structure is formed.

After the communicative backbone is established, OLMo-2-1B undergoes a sustained decline in cross-layer alignment (Table 2). Averaged across all boundaries, OLMo’s mean coherence drops from 0.472 to 0.256 over the course of training, a 46% decline, with the steepest reduction (22%) occurring between steps 10k and 100k. Pythia-1B shows a softer overall decline of 14% across its remaining training window (steps 8k to 143,000).

Pythia-1.4B declines even less on average (9%), though its near-output layers (boundaries 17–22) drop 42% from their step-2,000 peak. This resembles the OLMo pattern locally, although unlike OLMo, Pythia-1.4B’s mid-depth layers (11–16) remain stable.

Model	Step	Pairs > 0.15	Mean $d=1$	Mean $d=3$	Mean $d=5$
OLMo-2-1B	10,000	64/120 (53%)	0.472	0.293	0.188
	100,000	41/120 (34%)	0.369	0.196	0.120
	1,000,000	24/120 (20%)	0.256	0.100	0.077
Pythia-1B	8,000	93/120 (78%)	0.482	0.342	0.253
	143,000	104/120 (87%)	0.417	0.313	0.233
Pythia-1.4B	8,000	225/276 (82%)	0.496	0.387	0.301
	143,000	252/276 (91%)	0.449	0.350	0.278

Table 3: Pairwise top-10 subspace overlap summary across late training for OLMo-2-1B, Pythia-1B, and Pythia-1.4B. “Pairs > 0.15” counts the fraction of all layer pairs with mean cosine similarity above 0.15 (a threshold well above the random baseline of ~ 0.06). Mean overlap at distance d is the average top-10 subspace overlap between all layer pairs separated by d layers. OLMo’s long-range structure dissolves progressively, while both Pythia models consolidate.

The near-output softening likely reflects redistribution within a strengthening global structure, which the pairwise data supports (Table 3). Despite the boundary-level softening in Table 2, both Pythia models consolidate their pairwise structure across training, increasing the fraction of meaningfully aligned layer pairs to 87% and 91% respectively. OLMo moves in the opposite direction: by step 1M, only 20% of pairs remain above the 0.15 threshold, and its distance-5 overlap (0.077) is effectively at the random baseline.

This divergence is difficult to attribute to training duration alone. If weight-level decoherence were simply what happens given enough training steps, we would expect at least the beginning of that trend in Pythia’s late checkpoints. Instead, the Pythia models consolidate. The dissolution in OLMo requires a mechanism that is absent in Pythia.

The most significant architectural difference between the two model families is the MLP activation function. Pythia uses GELU, a fixed element-wise nonlinearity. OLMo uses SwiGLU, which introduces a third learned weight matrix (W_{gate}). In a GELU MLP, the composed transformation is effectively determined by W_{down} and W_{up} ; cross-layer subspace alignment in these matrices is both necessary and sufficient for inter-layer communication. In a SwiGLU MLP, the effective transformation is $W_{\text{down}} \cdot \text{diag}(g(\mathbf{x})) \cdot W_{\text{up}}$, where $g(\mathbf{x}) = \text{SiLU}(W_{\text{gate}} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ depends on the input. This means the weight-level subspace analysis that captures the full communicative structure in Pythia captures only the static component in OLMo, missing whatever coordination the gate provides.

The gate’s behavior varies by depth, and this variation explains the anomalous increase in early-layer coherence shown in Table 2.

	Step 10,000	Step 100,000	Step 1,000,000
<i>Gate sparsity</i>			
Layer 0	0.135	0.709	0.619
Layer 4	0.142	0.563	0.430
Layer 8	0.157	0.321	0.316
Layer 11	0.246	0.205	0.232
Layer 15	0.478	0.157	0.156
<i>Gate Jaccard similarity (adjacent layers)</i>			
Boundary 0–1	0.775	0.208	0.274
Boundary 4–5	0.753	0.328	0.450
Boundary 8–9	0.715	0.535	0.534
Boundary 11–12	0.564	0.683	0.658
Boundary 14–15	0.375	0.750	0.727

Table 4: Gate sparsity (fraction of gate dimensions with activation below 0.1) and adjacent-layer gate Jaccard similarity for OLMo-2-1B across training. At step 10,000, the late layers are the most sparse and the early layers show the highest gate Jaccard; by step 1,000,000, both gradients have inverted, with early layers gating off the majority of their dimensions while late layers coordinate through shared active dimensions.

By step 1M, gate activations at OLMo’s early layers have become highly sparse (over 60% of dimensions gated off at layer 0), while the late layers remain dense (16% gated off at layer 15). This gradient, which reverses the pattern at step 10k, restructures how adjacent layers coordinate: at early boundaries, each layer develops its own sparse routing pattern (Jaccard drops from 0.78 to 0.27), while at late boundaries, adjacent layers activate nearly identical subsets of gate dimensions (Jaccard rises from 0.38 to 0.73). At the late layers, the gate takes over the coordination role from the static weights.

Between steps 10k and 1M, mean weight-level overlap at boundaries 12–14 drops from 0.570 to 0.298, while gate Jaccard similarity rises from 0.431 to 0.711 (Table 5). Adjacent late layers activate nearly identical subsets of gate dimensions, ensuring they process information through a shared effective subspace even as their static weight subspaces diverge. At the early layers, the opposite occurs: gate Jaccard drops from 0.769 to 0.321 as each layer develops its own sparse routing pattern, while weight-level overlap modestly increases.

The weight-level decoherence documented in Tables 2 and 3 seems to reflect a transfer of coordination from static weights to the input-dependent gate, concentrated at the layers closest to the output. This interpretation is moderately supported by the relationship between the two metrics across depth: the change in weight overlap from 10k to 1M is anti-correlated with the change in gate Jaccard across all 15 boundaries ($r = -0.59$), consistent with coordination shifting from one mechanism to the other.

3.3 TinyLlama and BLOOM

The decoherence documented above could be specific to OLMo rather than a general property of SwiGLU architectures, and the consolidation observed in Pythia could reflect its parallel attention-MLP ordering rather than its GELU activation. To disentangle these variables, we repeat the pairwise analysis on two additional models: TinyLlama-1.1B (22 layers, 2048-dim, SwiGLU) and BLOOM-1.1B (24 layers, 1536-dim, GELU). TinyLlama tests whether the decoherence pattern replicates in a

Boundary	Weight overlap		Gate Jaccard	
	Step 10k	Step 1M	Step 10k	Step 1M
Early (mean of 0–1, 1–2, 2–3)	0.164	0.202 (+23%)	0.769	0.321 (–58%)
Late (mean of 12–13, 13–14, 14–15)	0.570	0.298 (–48%)	0.431	0.711 (+65%)

Table 5: Weight-level subspace overlap (top-10 mean cosine similarity of $W_{down}W_{up}$) and gate-level coordination (Jaccard similarity of active gate dimensions) between adjacent layers at early and late boundaries for OLMo-2-1B, at steps 10,000 and 1,000,000. At the late boundaries, weight-level overlap drops while gate Jaccard rises, indicating a transfer of coordination from static weights to the input-dependent gate. At the early boundaries, the pattern reverses.

SwiGLU model from a different family than OLMo. BLOOM provides a separate dissociation: like OLMo and TinyLlama, it uses a sequential attention-MLP ordering, but like Pythia, it uses a GELU activation. If the divergence is driven by the activation function, BLOOM should consolidate like Pythia despite sharing OLMo’s sequential layout. Neither model provides dense early checkpoints, so we cannot use them to confirm propagation dynamics, but they can adjudicate the activation function question directly.

The results cleanly separate the two variables (Table 6). TinyLlama shows the same progressive dissolution of pairwise structure observed in OLMo: the fraction of meaningfully aligned layer pairs falls from 71% to 29% over the course of training, with mean overlap at distance 5 dropping from 0.224 to 0.128, approaching the random baseline. BLOOM, despite training for 600,000 steps and sharing OLMo’s sequential architecture, stabilizes at 81% after an initial contraction, with its long-range structure remaining well above baseline throughout. This pattern matches the consolidation observed in the Pythia models, confirming that the divergence tracks the activation function rather than the attention-MLP ordering.

Model	Step	Pairs > 0.15	Mean $d=1$	Mean $d=3$	Mean $d=5$
TinyLlama-1.1B	50,000	165/231 (71%)	0.441	0.304	0.224
	240,000	100/231 (43%)	0.335	0.232	0.160
	480,000	73/231 (32%)	0.318	0.195	0.137
	1,431,000	67/231 (29%)	0.304	0.174	0.128
BLOOM-1.1B	1,000	276/276 (100%)	0.733	0.481	0.395
	300,000	224/276 (81%)	0.600	0.398	0.287
	500,000	224/276 (81%)	0.580	0.382	0.273
	600,000	228/276 (83%)	0.569	0.379	0.269

Table 6: Pairwise top-10 subspace overlap summary across training for TinyLlama-1.1B and BLOOM-1.1B. TinyLlama (SwiGLU) shows rapid dissolution of pairwise structure, dropping from 71% to 43% to 32% across steps 50,000, 240,000, and 480,000. BLOOM (GELU) stabilizes at 81% after an initial contraction, and shows signs of reconsolidation between steps 500,000 and 600,000.

TinyLlama’s gate activation pattern mirrors OLMo’s end-state (Table 8). By the final checkpoint, gate sparsity ranges from 96% at layer 0 to 26% at layer 21, and gate Jaccard similarity between adjacent layers rises monotonically from 0.02 at the earliest boundary to 0.58 at the latest. The depth gradient is present at the earliest available checkpoint (step 50k), consistent with the transfer having occurred earlier in training, although the gradient compresses over the remaining steps: late-boundary Jaccard decreases (e.g., 0.72 to 0.58 at boundary 20–21) while early-boundary values modestly increase, suggesting ongoing redistribution even after the broad pattern is set.

4 Discussion

The six models we examined, spanning two architectural families, reveal a common developmental sequence with a consistent ordering of events, even as the details vary with architecture and scale.

The first phase is the establishment of a communicative backbone. Early in training, adjacent layers align their dominant MLP transformation directions, creating a shared set of residual stream subspaces through which information can accumulate coherently across depth. This alignment begins at the points in the network where signals are least corrupted. In the Pythia models, the parallel organization of the attention and MLP blocks means the first and final MLP block both receive clean signals. As a result, both endpoints commit early, producing competing protocols that are eventually resolved in favor of the output end. For OLMo, we see cross-layer alignment emerging only from the output end. In both families, the output-anchored alignment dominates, and the direction of propagation is consistently backward through the network.

The second phase is spectral restructuring. Once layers have agreed on which directions to use, training reshapes the singular value spectra of individual layers to reflect that agreement; directions that are aligned across layers carry a consistent gradient signal and are amplified. The result is a bulk-tail separation in which a small number of structurally significant directions pull away from an otherwise flat spectrum. In the Pythia models, this restructuring is temporally dissociated from the initial alignment, beginning only after the communicative backbone is in place. In OLMo, the two processes overlap in time, though alignment decelerates as spectral restructuring accelerates within the overlapping window. The limited checkpoint density in OLMo’s earliest training steps prevents a definitive determination of whether the overlap reflects a compressed version of the same sequence or a genuinely different ordering.

What follows these two shared phases is an extended period of elaboration whose character depends on the activation function. In the GELU models, weight-level alignment holds mostly steady, the depth gradient that emerged during spectral restructuring continues to sharpen, and the fraction of meaningfully aligned layer pairs increases through the final checkpoint. The backbone, once built, serves as permanent scaffolding. In the SwiGLU models, the weight-level backbone progressively dissolves. Cross-layer alignment declines at nearly every boundary, long-range subspace overlap falls toward the random baseline, and the coordination role transfers from static weight subspaces to the input-dependent gate. The backbone is built and then replaced by a system in which adjacent layers dynamically select a shared effective subspace on each forward pass, coordinating through an input-dependent gating of which dimensions to activate.

4.1 Static and dynamic communication strategies

The distinction between GELU and SwiGLU models maps onto a distinction that has been extensively documented in cortical communication. In early sensory areas, inter-area communication occurs through relatively stable, low-dimensional subspaces whose geometry is largely invariant to stimulus or task context. Semedo et al. [2019] showed that the communication subspace between V1 and V2 is low-rank, consistent across stimuli, and distinct from the dominant patterns of V1’s internal activity. Srinath et al. [2021] found that attentional shifts modulated the amount of information flowing through the MT–SC communication subspace without substantially altering its geometry. These are fixed channels, and what varies is how much signal is routed through them.

In associative and prefrontal regions, a different strategy predominates. Communication subspaces between hippocampus and prefrontal cortex are modulated by network oscillations and behavioral state [Young et al., 2025], and a single source population can maintain multiple overlapping subspaces for routing to different downstream targets, selectively activating different ones depending on task demands [MacDowell et al., 2025]. Here, the channel is dynamic; moment-to-moment activations determine the structure of coordination.

The GELU models in our study resemble the first pattern. Their weight-level communication protocol, once established, consolidates and persists. The fraction of meaningfully aligned layer pairs increases through the final checkpoint, and the subspace geometry is fixed in the weights themselves, independent of the input being processed. The SwiGLU models resemble the second. Their static weight subspaces dissolve, and coordination transfers to the gate. This gate selects a shared set of active dimensions on each forward pass as a function of the input, effectively defining an input-dependent subspace through which adjacent layers coordinate. The depth gradient we observe in gate coordination reinforces the parallel: late layers, which sit closest to the loss and must route the most task-relevant information, develop the densest and most coordinated gate patterns, while early layers develop sparse, idiosyncratic routing. This echoes the cortical gradient in which associative

regions, which integrate across the most diverse inputs, show the most dynamic communication; early sensory areas, which process more stereotyped signals, rely on more fixed channels.

The mechanisms behind these parallels are, of course, entirely different. What we are observing is a convergence at the level of computational strategy. Two systems facing the same abstract problem of coordinating computation across independently operating modules through shared bandwidth arrived at the same pair of solutions: fixed-geometry channels and input-dependent channel selection. This distinction emerges from the problem structure rather than the implementation substrate, suggesting that it may be one of the few fundamental design decisions available to any modular system that must coordinate through a shared, finite-dimensional communication medium.

Preliminary analysis of the attention mechanism’s OV circuit supports this interpretation and suggests that the static/dynamic distinction reflects a general structural property rather than something specific to the activation function. We computed the combined OV product at each layer (summing $W_O W_V$ across heads) and measured cross-layer subspace overlap using the same methods applied to the MLP. In all three Pythia models, OV alignment follows the same early trajectory as MLP alignment: it surges during backbone formation, follows the same backward cascade from the output layers, and peaks between steps 512 and 2,000. But unlike the MLP, OV alignment then collapses. In Pythia-1.4B, mean adjacent-layer OV overlap (top-10) rises from 0.059 at initialization to 0.406 at step 2,000, then falls to 0.149 by step 8,000 and never recovers, while MLP overlap at the same boundaries remains above 0.45 throughout.

Unlike the Pythia models, OLMo’s OV alignment shows no output-anchored depth gradient during formation: at step 1,000, when MLP alignment is already developing the backward cascade documented in Section 3.1, OV overlap is flat at baseline across all 15 boundaries. At later checkpoints, the OV depth gradient that does emerge is inverted relative to the MLPs’: by step 1,000,000, OV alignment at the late boundaries (10–14) has fallen to near-baseline levels (mean 0.098), while the early boundaries (0–4) retain modest alignment (mean 0.200). This inversion maps onto the gate coordination gradient documented in Table 5: the late boundaries are where gate Jaccard is highest and where the gate has most strongly assumed the coordination role, suggesting that both MLP weight alignment and OV weight alignment become dispensable where the gate provides input-dependent coordination.

Despite these differences, the broad pattern across both architectures is consistent: the GELU MLP is the only mechanism in any of the models we examined where weight-level alignment persists through the final checkpoint. Both the OV circuit and the SwiGLU MLP interpose an input-dependent transformation between their static projection matrices (the attention pattern and the gate, respectively), and in both cases, static weight-level alignment either collapses or fails to develop strongly. This suggests that the relevant variable is whether the transformation contains an input-dependent component that can assume the coordination role. Where such a component exists, static alignment appears to serve as a transient scaffold at most; where it does not, as in the GELU MLP, static alignment is the coordination mechanism.

4.2 Limitations and future directions

All six models in this study are at or below 1.4B parameters. The developmental sequence we document could look different at scale, where the residual stream is much higher-dimensional and the ratio of computational dimensions to communication bandwidth shifts substantially. It is possible, for instance, that larger models develop communicative structure more gradually, that the backward cascade operates differently when there are hundreds of layers rather than two dozen, or that the depth gradient in spectral specialization takes a qualitatively different form. Whether the ordering of phases we report here is a universal feature of transformer training or a property of the small-model regime is an open question.

Our analysis of the attention mechanism is preliminary, limited to the combined OV product rather than individual heads or QK circuits. A complete account would need to examine whether specific head types align with the MLP-level developmental sequence we identify, and whether attention and MLP communication channels interact or develop independently.

More broadly, we do not establish a causal link between the developmental phases we document and the acquisition of specific model capabilities. The communicative backbone forms early and appears to organize subsequent structural development, but whether its formation corresponds to the induction

head phase change, and whether spectral restructuring coincides with the emergence of more complex circuits, remains untested. Connecting the structural developmental sequence to a functional one would substantially strengthen the account, but constitutes a separate research program.

For SwiGLU models specifically, our weight-level analysis captures only the static component of the communicative protocol, and the gate Jaccard metric, while informative, is a coarse measure that tells us which dimensions are co-active across adjacent layers without revealing how those active dimensions are geometrically configured. A more complete characterization would require computing the principal angles of the input-conditioned effective transformation, $W_{\text{down}} \cdot \text{diag}(g(\mathbf{x})) \cdot W_{\text{up}}$, across layers for specific inputs. This is computationally demanding but would answer an open question: whether the dynamic subspaces selected by the gate follow the same developmental sequence (early alignment, spectral restructuring, depth specialization) that the static subspaces follow in GELU models. This limitation also carries a practical consequence for interpretability. Weight-based analysis tools, including composition scores [Elhage et al., 2021] and SVD-based circuit discovery [Merullo et al., 2024], may underestimate or miss the coordination structure in SwiGLU models, since the communicative protocol increasingly resides in the gate activations rather than the static weights. Similarly, pruning and compression methods that rely on weight-level coherence to assess layer importance could erroneously flag late SwiGLU layers as redundant, when our data suggest these are the most tightly coordinated layers in the model through their gate patterns.

Finally, the temporal resolution of available checkpoints constrains what we can conclude about the ordering of developmental events. Denser early checkpoints, or controlled training runs with matched checkpoint schedules across architectures, would resolve this ambiguity.

5 Conclusion

The central finding of this paper is one of developmental priority. One of the first things a transformer model must learn is how to communicate across layers, and once communication is established, intelligent computation can emerge. The communication protocol forms rapidly, propagates as a backward cascade from the output layers, and is followed by spectral and structural elaboration that builds on the directions it establishes.

The form the mature protocol takes depends on the activation function, with GELU models maintaining fixed-geometry channels and SwiGLU models transitioning to input-dependent subspace selection through a learned gate. Our preliminary findings show a similar phenomenon in attention blocks. It is likely not a coincidence that the architectural components that have proven most capable in practice, both attention and SwiGLU, are those that develop dynamic rather than static communication strategies. This suggests that input-dependent coordination is the more expressive alternative to fixed-geometry channels.

More broadly, these results point toward a view of transformer training as a structured developmental process with identifiable phases and consistent ordering, rather than a monolithic optimization. Characterizing this process at the level of communicative infrastructure, rather than individual circuits or capabilities, may offer a productive complement to existing approaches in mechanistic interpretability.

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A Technical appendices

A.1 OLMo redistribution detail

Model	Step 1,000		Step 2,000		Step 5,000	
	top-5	top-50	top-5	top-50	top-5	top-50
<i>Final layer boundary</i>						
OLMo-2-1B	0.242	0.168	0.625	0.329	0.577 (-8%)	0.434 (+32%)
<i>Middle layer boundary (layer 7–8)</i>						
OLMo-2-1B	0.074	0.135	0.189	0.170	0.419 (+122%)	0.495 (+191%)

Table 7: Mean cosine similarity between top- k singular vector subspaces at the final and middle layer boundaries for OLMo-2-1B, at steps 1,000, 2,000, and 5,000. Percentage changes are computed from step 2,000 to step 5,000. At the final boundary, top-5 overlap drops 8% and top-50 rises, indicating the same redistribution from a narrow beam into a broader subspace observed in the Pythia models. At the middle boundary, all subspace widths increase uniformly, with gains exceeding 100%, reflecting the alignment wave arriving later at interior layers.

A.2 TinyLlama gate statistics

	Step 50,000	Step 1,431,000
<i>Gate sparsity</i>		
Layer 0	0.987	0.963
Layer 4	0.865	0.799
Layer 8	0.520	0.562
Layer 11	0.358	0.452
Layer 15	0.267	0.366
Layer 21	0.159	0.256
<i>Gate Jaccard similarity (adjacent layers)</i>		
Boundary 0–1	0.007	0.015
Boundary 4–5	0.093	0.131
Boundary 8–9	0.345	0.314
Boundary 11–12	0.496	0.410
Boundary 15–16	0.594	0.506
Boundary 20–21	0.723	0.583

Table 8: Gate sparsity (fraction of gate dimensions with activation below 0.1) and adjacent-layer gate Jaccard similarity for TinyLlama-1.1B at steps 50,000 and 1,431,000. Both metrics show a strong depth gradient at the earliest available checkpoint, although the gradient compresses over training: late-boundary Jaccard decreases while early-boundary Jaccard modestly increases.